

HIGH COURAGE OF WAR AND LABOR VETERANS IN DEFENDING THE MOTHERLAND IN EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM

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Annotation

in this article, a scientific and practical conversation was held with the young generation about the great work done by our grandfathers for us. To give students an understanding of traditions. Elucidating the educational significance of martial traditions. Information is provided on teaching students to use HVT forms and techniques

Key words

Army, war, labor veterans, youth, education, fleet, battle.

ВЫСОКОЕ МУЖЕСТВО ВЕТЕРАНОВ ВОЙНЫ И ТРУДА В ЗАЩИТЕ РОДИНЫ В ВОСПИТАНИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ В ДУХЕ ПАТРИОТИЗМА

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Аннотация

в данной статье была проведена научно-практическая беседа с молодым поколением о великой работе, проделанной для нас нашими дедками. Чтобы дать учащимся представление о традициях. Выяснение воспитательного значения боевых традиций. Представлена информация по обучению студентов использованию форм и приемов ТГВ.

Ключевые слова

Армия, война, ветераны труда, молодежь, воспитание, флот, бой.

YOSHLARNI VATANPARVARLIK RUXIDA TARBIYALASHDA URUSH VA MEHNAT FAXRIYLARINING VATANNI HIMOYA QILISHDAGI YUKSAK JASORATLARI

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodga kata yoshdagi bobolarimizni biz uchun qilgan yuksak ishlari haqida ilmiy a'maliy suhbat bo'lib o'tgan. Talabalarga an'analar haqida tushuncha berish. Jangovar an'analarni tarbiyaviy ahamiyatni yoritib berish. Talabalarga HVT shakl va uslublaridan foydalanishni o'rgatish haqida ma'lumot berilgan

Kalit so'zlar

Armiya, urush, mahnat faxriylari, yoshlar, tarbiya, flot, jang.

*Every brave, every righteous person brings glory to the Motherland
(Roman Rollan)*

Love for the Motherland and constant preparation for its defense are formed on the basis of military traditions that invite soldiers to battle in armies and navies, appear during military service and are passed from generation to generation. There are ideas of loyalty to the Military Oath, the battle flag, friendship in battle, respect for the commander, protection of him in battle, intelligence in battle and mercy to enemies.

Loyalty to the motherland is a historical tradition, which lived in the consciousness of society in every socio-ethnic form. Historical names include Tomaris (Kir II), Shiroq, Spitamen, Muqanna, Amir Temur.

Uprisings of Tashkent, Fergana, Jizzakh. Uzbeks' heroism in the battles against the Nazis on the fronts of World War II, heroism in the fields, factories. The fact that people accept the evacuees into their families even if they are helpless, and eat the last bite of bread in a friendly manner even if they are hungry, shows that Uzbekistan is once again a philanthropist.

Loyalty to the Battle Flag and Military Oath.

Since ancient times, the battle flag has been placed as a symbol calling warriors to battle. In ancient times, the flag consisted of a bundle of grass on the end of a long stick or tied to the end of a horse's bridle. Later, it was replaced with a piece of cloth.

The flag has long been a symbol of war. A battle oath was taken under the Battle Flag. Loyalty to the Battle Flag is a great tradition. It has ancient origins. The flag is sacred.

During the war years, it was carefully guarded like the apple of an eye, like the greatest and most valuable property. The Battle Flag of the Armed Forces shows the status of the military units of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The battle flag of a military unit is a symbol of glory.

The importance of martial traditions in youth education.

The Armed Forces of Uzbekistan are an integral part of the nation. Our best military and labor traditions, which arose during our centuries-old history, have not lost their rich spiritual power. His spiritual abilities are very high and are still appreciated. It has deep resources.

Unyielding Sogdiya and Bactria, Morocco and Khorezmshah, the bravery of Shiroq in the desert for the freedom of the people (1st century BC, Darius I) and the revolt of Spitamen (324-327 BC) Leaders A. Makedonsky, Abru (against Turkestan in the 80s of the 6th century), Muqanna (against the Arabs in the 70s of the 8th century) showed unforgettable courage.

Great generals Amir Temur (1336 - 1405) and his descendants. Babur (the founder of the great Mongol dynasty, 15th - 16th centuries) - all these are our national values that have come down to us from history and have become a spiritual heritage, that is, our spiritual and educational wealth. Our great ancestors Beruni (scientist 973-1050), Al-Khorazmi (mathematician, geographer, historian 780-847), Ibn Sina (Aviasenna, medicine, astronomy, geology 980-1037), Imam Bukhari, Ahmad Yassavi, Ulugbek (school of astrology, statesman 1394 - 1449 y.) the memory of our scientists will last forever and will occupy positive places in people's hearts.

On the fronts of the Second World War, Uzbek fighters showed bravery in a manner worthy of the traditions of our great ancestors.

For example, Sabir Rakhimov, Akhmadjon Kurbanov, Toshtemir Rustamov, Kudrat Suyunov, Yelena Stempkovskaya. Voldemar Mayapid and many other warriors and others showed heroism defending our Motherland.

More than 120 thousand of our compatriots were awarded with orders and medals. More than 300 of them were awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union, and 58 fighters were awarded the Order of Fame of the 3rd degree.

We will always remember those who sacrificed their lives for their Motherland on the battlefields, heroically defended it, and contributed to domestic demand with their labor. "As long as we live on earth, we bow before the bravery of our heroes and their memory." I.A. Karimov. Oliy Majlis 2nd session May 3, 1998.

Educating young people based on the martial and labor traditions of our people is one of the activities of our educational institution.

Tradition is a noteworthy, existing social and economic attitude passed down from generation to generation, and a connection with the social and political system of society. Production methods and methods, which are embedded in people's minds during a certain period of time and are always encountered in their lives, as well as dominant political consciousness, are developing day by day. In short, tradition is one of our national and universal human qualities, passed from one generation to another. The traditional love of the Uzbek people for Uzbekistan, its land, nature, and people, the desire to know the traditions, culture, and history of our country. It includes being proud of the achievements and power of our republic and others. Education of young people is based on the experience of our ancestors.

Traditions are determined by the specific historical basis of the nation, they cannot be taken from one nation and absorbed into another. Every nation has its own traditions. Some of them may have something in common. For example: In the armies of many countries, martial traditions consist of labor traditions such as acquiring military knowledge and loving one's profession.

There are also traditions that belong only to this people, nation or region.

In the example of Uzbek traditions and customs, the heart and nature of the people finds its indelible reflection: hard work, hospitality, kindness, respect for adults, childhood, love of nature and friendship.

Thanks to independence, all the values of our people were restored. For this reason, it is necessary for our youth to know the traditions and customs of the country where they live. For example, the hospitality of Uzbeks is based on deep respect for people. When a guest comes to the house, the host does not spare

everything in the house, he considers it his duty to honor the hospitality. We can cite the following few Uzbek folk proverbs as proof of these thoughts. For example: "The guest is as great as your father", "If there is a guest in your house, don't even chase the cat, it can be explained that the guest is saying this to his honor", "If there is no bread in your house, let him replace it with a sweet word". "If you tell the guest not to leave, don't bring the food." Because everyone knows that it is disrespectful to get up before dinner in Uzbekistan.

Traditions of hospitality are a common feature of this society. An example of this is the assistance provided to families displaced from the lands occupied by the enemy during the Second World War. Thousands of people have found their peace here, for many Uzbekistan has become their homeland. Children who lost their parents in Uzbek families began to grow up. A monument to the blacksmith Shomakhmud Ota and his wife Bahri Aya was erected in the People's Friendship Square of our capital.